

Assessment of Copper Sulphate and Silver Nanoparticles for the management of Post-incidence of Black Sigatoka disease of Plantain (*Musa spp.*)

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Abstract

Black Sigatoka is a significant plantain disease caused by *Mycosphaerella fijiensis*. The study assessed the effect of copper sulphate and silver nanoparticles for managing post-incidence of black Sigatoka disease of plantain. Concentrations of 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 g/L each of copper sulphate and silver nanoparticles, were applied after visual observation of the disease. The plots of carbendazim served as positive control while the untreated control (0 g/L) was the negative control. At the 14th week after transplanting, the least disease severity of 2.52 was recorded when 0.05 g/L silver nanoparticles was applied while 0.05 g/L copper sulphate had 2.93 severity, which was not significantly different ($p \geq 0.05$) from 3.15 severity recorded for plantain sprayed with carbendazim. The result showed that 0.05 g/L silver nanoparticles reduced the disease severity by 58% and 0.05 g/L copper sulphate by 51.17% compared with the untreated control plots. Hence, application of silver nanoparticles at 0.05 g/L concentration would be a better option for plantain farmers in curtailing post-incidence emergence of black Sigatoka of plantain. Aside being a significant nanopesticide, biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using plant extracts would be a greener approach than chemical synthesis while the shift from conventional copper sulphate to nano-enabled applications would reduce dosage and environmental impact.

Keywords: Copper sulphate, incidence, *Mycosphaerella fijiensis*, plantain, severity, silver nanoparticles.

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Introduction

In humid tropical Africa, plantains are one of the best sources of carbohydrates with 35% carbohydrates, fats range between 0.2 and 0.5%, while protein and ash are 1.2%, and 0.8%, respectively (Irie et al., 2024). Research by Oyedele et al. (2022) suggests that they could help reduce rural poverty and improve national food security. They are also high in dietary fiber, which is important for lowering cholesterol, preventing constipation, and lowering blood pressure (Tsado et al., 2021). They also contain significant amounts of potassium, magnesium, and phosphate, but are

low in fat due to their potassium content (Al-Snafi et al., 2023). Compared to bananas, plantains have more starch, which is slowly broken down in the body when consumed (Ávila-Martín et al., 2025). This characteristic is highly valued by diabetics because it helps regulate blood sugar levels, especially when it comes to unripe plantains (Al-Snafi et al., 2023). In Nigeria, plantain consumption has significantly grown presently owing to the country's fast urbanization and the high demand for quick and easy meals by the city's non-farming residents (Ademola and Dania, 2024).

According to Drenth and Kema (2021), sigatoka disease is one of the major diseases that pose a threat to plantain production worldwide. *Mycosphaerella* spp. cause sigatoka disease (Drenth and Kema (2021), and as the disease advances to advanced stages, it affects a large photosynthetic area of the leaf, causing premature leaf fall and fruit ripening (Holdings and Lanka, 2023). *Mycosphaerella fijiensis* Morelet is responsible for Black sigatoka disease (Mengesha et al., 2023). Its culture is dark brown. The conidia are septate, pale brown, smooth-walled with oclavate to subcylindrical in shape that are borne on specialized stalks of conidiophores (Ademola and Dania, 2024). The disease is widespread among banana plantations throughout Nigeria with an associated reduction in farmers' income, causing harvested fruits from infected plants to ripen prematurely and reducing the quantity and quality of crops (Ademola and Dania, 2024). The lesions reduce the photosynthetic potential of the infected leaves and yield losses have been reported to vary between 40 and 60% in susceptible varieties (Barekye et al., 2011; Ugarteet et al., 2020).

Mimouni et al. (2025) investigated the effectiveness of copper sulphate in controlling the bacteria *Pseudomonas corrugata* and *Clavibacter michiganensis* on tomato, but few studies have demonstrated the fungicidal effects of silver nanoparticles against a number of phytopathogenic fungi (Yassin et al., 2021). Nanoparticles (NPs) is thought to be a promising alternative method of controlling phytopathogens (Malik et al., 2024), and the application of silver and gold NPs in particular produced positive results on various crop plants with little to no phytotoxicity (Murugan et al., 2025).

Materials and Methods

Description of the trial location

The trial was carried out in Ogun State, Nigeria, at the Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta (FUNAAB) DelPHE-5 Research farm. FUNAAB is situated on latitude 7°20' N and longitude 3°23' E (Ganiyu et al., 2024). In 2022, the rainfall pattern, temperature ranges, humidity and the soil characteristics of the location are explained as contained in Olanrewaju et al. (2022).

Source of plantain suckers

Approximately three-month-old plantain suckers (cv. Giant elephant) of uniform height and stem girth were sourced from Institute of Agricultural Research & Training (IAR&T), Moor Plantation, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Land Preparation, experimental design and transplanting

Land was ploughed and after a month, harrowed. The experimental plots were mapped out with border row of 2 m, and plots laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) using three replications. Plantain suckers were transplanted (a sucker per hole) at the depth ranged from 25 to 30 cm with intra and inter row spacing of 3 m x 3 m, respectively. Transplanting was done on May 15, 2022.

Isolation and identification of Mycosphaerella fijiensis

After the termination of the field experiment, leaves with Sigatoka lesions from the plantain(s) were harvested and were taken to the laboratory. The disease-affected leaf portions were cut into small pieces (approximately 4 x 4 cm), surface sterilised in 70% alcohol for 30 seconds, washed with sterile distilled water three times, then allowed to air-dry before plating on potato dextrose agar (PDA) containing 0.6 mg/ml, streptomycin. Incubation was done at room temperature (28±2°C) for five days, during which time the fungal outgrowths were isolated using the techniques of Kumakech et al. (2022). Pure cultures of the isolates were acquired and stored on PDA slants in the refrigerator at 4 °C prior to use. Pure fungal isolates were identified on the basis of their morphological features, according to standard procedures of Samson et al. (2010).

Pathogenicity test on plantain

The youngest expanded leaves of plantains were used in the pathogenicity test, which was conducted using the leaf segment method of Kumakech et al. (2022). Briefly, sections of the youngest leaves, measuring roughly 7 cm by 7 cm, were cut under sterile distilled water, surface sterilised with 70% alcohol for 30 seconds, and wash three times with sterile distilled water. Each leaf surface, adaxial, was placed in a Petri dish lined with sterile moistened tissue paper. This was done by lightly

pricking the middle of each leaf segment with a sterile needle. In order to avoid contact with the moistened tissue paper, three sterile glass rods were positioned underneath the leaf segments. The injured portion of a leaf segment was then inoculated with a 5 mm agar disc from a 5-day-old culture of *M. fijiensis* with the mycelial surface in contact with the leaf, while the uninoculated but injured leaf segments served as a control. Incubation of plates was for seven days at room temperature, with observations made every 24 hours for the onset of disease symptoms. Following the incubation period, *M. fijiensis* was re-isolated from the infected leaf sections as previously described.

Treatments, application of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and the copper sulphate (CuSO₄), and Field management

Copper sulphate (CuSO₄) was sourced from the Plant Tissue Culture Laboratory of the Department of Crop Protection, FUNAAB while silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) (20-30 nm, WACV) were sourced from Beijing Nano Co. Ltd (China) at 1 g/L initial concentration. The experiment consisted of plantain suckers (cv. Giant elephant) and three concentrations (0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 g/L) each of both the AgNPs and CuSO₄. Carbendazim (1g/L) served as positive

control while the untreated control plots received no application. Silver nanoparticles were reconstituted to different concentration using the formula; $C_1V_1=C_2V_2$, where C_1 = concentration of the stock (1 g/L), V_1 = quantity of the stock required (L), C_2 = target concentration (g/L), and V_2 = final quantity (L). CuSO₄ and Carbendazim powders were appropriately weighed into sterile distilled water to make the different concentrations used. Using knapsack sprayer, treatments were foliar-applied, after visual observation of the disease, till run-off started 6th week after transplanting (WAT) and repeated at two-week interval till 14th week after transplanting while weeding was done as at when due.

Data collection and analysis

Data on plant height (cm), stem girth (cm), disease incidence (%) and severity were collected. Disease incidence (%) was calculated based on percentage number of infected leaves while the disease severity was evaluated on a 0–6-point scale of Ullah et al. (2025) as shown in Table below.

Scale	Description
0	no symptom of necrotic lesions
1	less than 1% necrotic lesions
2	1-5% necrotic lesions
3	6-15% necrotic lesions
4	16-33% necrotic lesions
5	34-50% necrotic lesions
6	51-100% necrotic lesions

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistical Analysis System (SAS), 9.1 packages, and means separated using the Duncan's Multiple Range Test ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results

Identity of *Mycosphaerella fijiensis*

The pathogen, *M. fijiensis*, formed slow-growing colonies on PDA that were initially white to grey, becoming dark olivaceous to black colonies with age. The colonies were typically velvety to slightly cottony in texture, later turning compact and leathery. The reverse side of the plate showed dark-brown to black.

Effect of AgNPs and CuSO₄ on post-incidence and severity of black Sigatoka disease of plantain

Table 1 shows the effect of AgNPs and CuSO₄ on black sigatoka of plantain. At 6 weeks after transplanting (WAT), no significant variation was found ($p \geq 0.05$) between treatments. However, at 8WAT, disease incidence of 55.34% was recorded for untreated control plots, which was

not significantly different from 50.00% and 60.00% disease incidence recorded for plantains sprayed with 0.01 g/L AgNPs and CuSO₄ concentrations, respectively but higher than and significantly different from 30.00%, 30.00%, 40.00%, 30.00%, and 31.67% incidence observed from plots sprayed with 0.05, 0.1 g/L AgNPs, 0.05, 0.1 g/L CuSO₄ and 1 g/L carbendazim, respectively. The highest and total disease incidence (100%) were recorded from untreated control plots at 10 to

14WAT, as well as when 0.01 g/L CuSO₄ was applied at 12 and 14WAT. At 12WAT, plots sprayed with 0.05 g/L AgNPs had the lowest disease incidence of 40.50% but was reduced to 40.00% at 14WAT. These values were not significantly different from 49.17% and 52.17% incidence recorded for plots sprayed with Carbendazim (1g/L) at 12 and 14WAT, respectively.

Table 1: Effect of AgNPs and CuSO₄ on post-incidence of black Sigatoka disease of plantain at 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14th weeks after transplanting

Treatment (g/L)	Black Sigatoka disease incidence (%)				
	6WAT	8WAT	10WAT	12WAT	14WAT
Control	10.00 ^a	55.34 ^a	100.00 ^a	100.00 ^a	100.00 ^a
AgNPs_0.01	10.33 ^a	50.00 ^a	60.00 ^b	66.67 ^b	80.67 ^a
AgNPs_0.05	10.00 ^a	30.00 ^b	40.00 ^c	40.50 ^c	40.00 ^b
AgNPs_0.1	10.00 ^a	20.00 ^b	30.00 ^c	60.00 ^b	80.00 ^a
CuSO₄_0.01	10.00 ^a	60.00 ^a	78.00 ^a	100.00 ^a	100.00 ^a
CuSO₄_0.05	10.00 ^a	40.00 ^b	45.00 ^b	50.00 ^c	55.00 ^b
CuSO₄_0.1	10.00 ^a	30.00 ^b	45.00 ^b	65.00 ^b	89.00 ^a
Carbendazim (1)	10.17 ^a	31.67 ^b	46.67 ^b	49.17 ^c	52.17 ^b

Means with the same superscript within a column are not significantly different ($p \geq 0.05$) according to Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) ($p \leq 0.05$); WAT=Weeks after transplanting; AgNPs = Silver nanoparticles; CuSO₄ = Copper sulphate.

Table 2 shows that at 6WAT, there was no significant variation in the outcome of the treatments on the plants. At 8WAT, disease severity ranged from 2.14 to 3.00. Effect for all data from disease severity was recorded when 0.05 g/L AgNPs was applied followed by 2.19 and 2.33 from plots treated with carbendazim and 0.05 g/L CuSO₄. At 10WAT, the least disease severity (2.54) was observed in plots treated with 0.05 g/L AgNPs, which was significantly

lower than 2.74, 2.83, 3.24 and 3.33 severity recorded in plots sprayed with carbendazim, 0.05 g/L CuSO₄, 0.1 and 0.01 g/L AgNPs, respectively. At 12WAT, the least sigatoka severity of 2.61 observed when 0.05 g/L AgNPs was applied, which was significantly lower than 3.00, 2.67, 4.38 and 4.33 disease severity for plots treated with carbendazim, 0.05 g/L CuSO₄, 0.1 and 0.01 g/L AgNPs, respectively. Similar trend was observed at 14WAT.

Table 2: Effect of AgNPs and CuSO₄ on severity of black Sigatoka disease of plantain at 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14th weeks after transplanting

Treatment (g/L)	Black Sigatoka disease severity index				
	6WAT	8WAT	10WAT	12WAT	14WAT
Control	1.64 ^a	2.57 ^a	5.26 ^a	6.00 ^a	6.00 ^a
AgNPs_0.01	1.00 ^a	2.83 ^a	3.33 ^b	4.33 ^b	5.33 ^a
AgNPs_0.05	1.00 ^a	2.14 ^b	2.54 ^c	2.61 ^c	2.52 ^b
AgNPs_0.1	1.17 ^a	2.80 ^a	3.24 ^b	4.38 ^b	5.05 ^a
CuSO₄_0.01	1.33 ^a	3.00 ^a	4.00 ^a	5.00 ^a	6.00 ^a
CuSO₄_0.05	1.00 ^a	2.33 ^b	2.83 ^b	2.67 ^b	2.93 ^b
CuSO₄_0.1	1.00 ^a	3.00 ^a	4.00 ^a	5.00 ^a	5.67 ^a
Carbendazim (1)	1.29 ^a	2.19 ^b	2.74 ^b	3.00 ^b	3.15 ^b

Means with the same superscript within a column are not significantly different ($p \geq 0.05$) according to Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) ($p \leq 0.05$); WAT=Weeks after transplanting; AgNPs = Silver nanoparticles; CuSO_4 = Copper sulphate.

Effect of AgNPs and CuSO_4 on plant height (cm) and stem girth (cm) of plantain

The overall range of the effect AgNPs and CuSO_4 on plantain height (cm) for the period of experiment was between 42.67 cm and 99.50 cm (Table 3). There were no significant differences in plantain height (cm) at 6 and 8WAT. At 14WAT, the highest plant height (99.50 cm) was observed in plots sprayed with 0.1 g/L CuSO_4 , though, not significantly different from the lowest plant height of 96.50 cm observed in plots sprayed with 0.01 and 0.05 g/L CuSO_4 , respectively. Stem girth ranged from 18.18 cm to 35.42 cm for the period of experiment. There were no significant differences in stem girth each week, between AgNPs, CuSO_4 and Carbendazim application for the period of experiment.

Discussion

According to Noar et al. (2022), the fungus that causes black sigatoka disease of plantains, *Mycosphaerella fijiensis*, transports through the stomata and is described by streaking lesions and cell death when fungal toxins are opened to light. Goenaga et al. (2021) showed that the underside of the third or fourth completely grown leaf had a little chlorotic fleck, which was the initial indication of black leaf streak on plantains. These flecks evolved into narrow, rusty brown streaks that frequently had truncated ends and sides that were severely constrained by the leaf veins, giving the plantains a streaky appearance. It was observed that, apart from the standard fungicide (Carbendazim), silver nanoparticles or copper sulphate could significantly decrease the effect of the disease. At the latter period of the experiment, carbendazim began to reveal significant disease reduction, lower than the highest concentration (0.1 g/L) of either silver nanoparticles or copper sulphate. This could be because of carbendazim being a common fungicide.

Silver nanoparticles at 0.05 g/L were found to be equivalent to synthetic fungicides (Carbendazim) in this investigation. According to

Taha et al. (2024), when compared to untreated control plots, the application of silver nanoparticles at lower concentrations decreased the incidence and severity of Fusarium wilt of tomato varieties. Copper sulfate and silver nanoparticles at 0.05 g/L were found to have encouraging potential in the treatment of plantain black sigatoka disease. Considering this, Mohamed et al. (2021) found that silver nanoparticles are more destructive to microbes than other metallic nanoparticles due to their antimicrobial properties.

Among all nanoparticles on the frontline of plant resistance, silver nanoparticles are distinct because they interfere with cell DNA, metabolic processes, and the electron transport chain, and nutrient intake of microorganisms, resulting in death (Khan et al., 2022). According to Bamal et al. (2021), nanosilver is less harmful to mammalian cells and more harmful to microbes. The fact that soil fertility was sufficient for plant growth and development and that copper sulphate and silver nanoparticles had no effect on plant development may be the cause of the non-significant variations in plantain height and stem girth that were observed.

Conclusion

Silver nanoparticles and copper sulphate at 0.05 g/L reduced the disease severity by 58% and 51.17%, respectively, compared with the control plots that were not treated. In this regard, silver nanoparticles displayed a better promising potential that made it a better option for plantain farmers. Hence, application of silver nanoparticles at 0.05 g/L concentration could curtail the harmful effects of *Mycosphaerella fijiensis* responsible for black sigatoka disease of plantain.

Aside being a significant nanopesticide, biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using plant extracts would be a greener approach than chemical synthesis while the shift from conventional copper sulphate to nano-enabled applications would reduce dosage and environmental impact.

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Table 3: Effect of AgNPs and CuSO₄ on plant height (cm) and stem girth (cm) of plantain at 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14th weeks after transplanting

Treatment (g/L)	6WAT		8WAT		10WAT		12WAT		14WAT	
	Plant height (cm)	Stem girth (cm)								
Control	50.63 ^a	18.18 ^a	60.78 ^a	22.06 ^a	68.35 ^a	25.06 ^a	77.25 ^a	30.38 ^a	97.75 ^a	32.47 ^a
AgNPs_0.01	54.17 ^a	21.50 ^a	66.00 ^a	22.58 ^a	72.25 ^a	26.78 ^a	83.92 ^a	30.99 ^a	98.08 ^a	33.58 ^a
AgNPs_0.05	42.67 ^a	21.75 ^a	64.00 ^a	23.60 ^a	74.58 ^a	28.08 ^a	81.33 ^a	32.00 ^a	96.92 ^a	35.42 ^a
AgNPs_0.1	49.50 ^a	21.17 ^a	63.00 ^a	22.75 ^a	78.50 ^a	28.25 ^a	81.00 ^a	32.25 ^a	96.58 ^a	34.50 ^a
CuSO₄_0.01	50.05 ^a	20.50 ^a	60.15 ^a	22.05 ^a	60.20 ^b	24.95 ^a	70.25 ^b	29.95 ^a	96.50 ^a	32.50 ^a
CuSO₄_0.05	45.00 ^a	20.00 ^a	66.55 ^a	23.50 ^a	70.50 ^a	26.45 ^a	80.71 ^a	31.55 ^a	96.50 ^a	34.50 ^a
CuSO₄_0.1	50.00 ^a	20.00 ^a	61.15 ^a	23.05 ^a	66.00 ^b	26.00 ^a	75.00 ^a	31.00 ^a	99.50 ^a	33.55 ^a
Carbendazim (1)	47.62 ^a	20.64 ^a	64.79 ^a	24.00 ^a	72.65 ^a	29.48 ^a	80.48 ^a	32.28 ^a	96.74 ^a	35.09 ^a

Means with the same superscript within a column are not significantly different ($p \geq 0.05$) according to Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) ($p \leq 0.05$); WAT=Weeks after transplanting; AgNPs = Silver nanoparticles; CuSO₄ = Copper sulphate.